

Studies on the Dependence of Optical Rotatory Power on Chemical Constitution. Part XI. The Rotatory Dispersion of Stereoisomeric *oo'*-Stilbene (*trans*) and *oo'*-Dibenzyl Derivatives of Bisimino-, Bisamino-, and Bisaminomethylene-camphors.

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The present communication is a continuation of Parts VIII and IX of this series and consists in the determination of the optical rotatory dispersion of the condensation products of oxymethylene camphors and camphorquinones with aromatic diamines, namely *oo'*-diaminostilbene and *oo'*-diaminodibenzyl. The measurements are made in six solvents as before.

The Effect of Conjugated Double Bonds and the Nature of the Solvent on Rotatory Power.—The remarkable effect of unsaturation and of conjugated linkages on optical activity has been noticed in previous publications (Forster and Thornley, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 95, 942 ; Singh and collaborators, *ibid*, 1919, 115, 566 ; 1920, 117, 980, 1599 ; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 545, 771). It is also brought out very clearly by comparing the structural formulæ depicted below, of the stilbene as well as the dibenzyl derivatives of bisiminocamphor, bisaminomethylenecamphor, and bisaminocamphor and their specific rotatory power in chloroform and pyridine (Table A). It is further seen that when the conjugation is broken at a distance from the asymmetric centre, the depression in the rotatory power is comparatively small (I→II and IV→V), but when the break in the conjugation occurs near that centre, there is considerable depression in the rotatory power (I→III ; IV→VI).

TABLE A.

Structural formula.		$[\alpha]^{35^\circ}$ $Hg_{green.}$ Chloroform. Pyridine.	
I.	C_8H_{14}	456°	574°
II.	C_8H_{14}	394	435
III.	C_8H_{14}	45.6	149.8
IV.	C_8H_{14}	684	880
V.	C_8H_{14}	392	374
VI.	C_8H_{14}	157	122.6

Certain unexpected irregularities are however noticed in connection with the optical activity of two series of compounds derived from *oo'*-diaminostilbene and *oo'*-diaminodibenzyl. It was to be expected that the corresponding compounds derived from *oo'*-diaminostilbene (I, II, III) would show greater rotation than those derived from *oo'*-diaminodibenzyl (IV, V, VI). But it was found that *oo'*-stilbene-bisiminocamphor (I) has lower rotation than *oo'*-dibenzylbisiminocamphor (IV) in all the solvents throughout the range of the spectrum investigated (compare Tables I—VI, IX—XIV; also Fig. I). Again *oo'*-stilbenebisaminocamphor (III) has lower rotatory power than *oo'*-dibenzylbisaminocamphor (VI) in chloroform solution but higher, as was expected, in pyridine. It is thus clear that the nature

of the solvent can bring about this abnormal behaviour in rotatory power.

A similar irregularity has previously been observed by Forster and Saville (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 789) in connection with the rotatory power of camphorylamino phenyliminocamphor (VII) which was expected to be less than that of *p*-phenylenebisiminocamphor (VIII) but it is greater.

The anomalous behaviour of camphorylamino phenyliminocamphor (VII) can however be explained by depicting the tautomeric formula (IX) for this compound.

The quinonoid arrangement postulated in this formula maintains an unbroken chain of conjugated double bonds and this explains its greater rotatory power. A similar explanation has already been advanced by us in the case of *pp'*-bisiminocamphordiphenylamine (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 1971) and *p*-iminocamphordiphenylamine (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 545 ; *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1930, 27, 347). It is likewise possible to bring in harmony the rotatory power of *oo'*-dibenzylbisiminocamphor with that of *oo'*-stilbenebisiminocamphor by postulating the following tautomeric arrangement for the former compound in which there is an unbroken chain of conjugated double bonds :

The Influence of Chemical Constitution and the Nature of Solvent on the Character of Rotatory Dispersion.—Oxymethylenecamphors and their condensation products with the aromatic diamines already described (*loc. cit.*) were found to obey the simple dispersion formula

of Drude, $[\alpha] = \frac{k}{\lambda^2 - \lambda_0^2}$, where k is the "rotation" constant and

λ_0^2 , the "dispersion" constant of the equation. The compounds described in this paper, with one exception, also obey the same relation. The wide applicability of the simple dispersion formula to varied types of organic compounds is thus further established.

FIG 1.

Rotatory Dispersion of oo'-Stilbenebisimino-d-camphor (1-6) and oo'-Dibenzylbisimino-d-camphor (7-12).

The very exact straight lines of Figs. I and II which are obtained by plotting $1/[\alpha]$ against λ^2 show that the dispersion is simple with the exception of *oo'*-dibenzylbisaminocamphor which exhibits "complex" rotatory dispersion in pyridine (Curve 6, Fig. 2) and benzene and for which, dispersion equations with three constants have been worked out (Tables XIX and XX). It is rather strange that the values of λ_0 lie in the infra-red region. It is not however

FIG 2.

Rotatory Dispersion in Pyridine ($t = 35^\circ$).

possible to represent the rotatory dispersion of *oo'*-dibenzylbisaminocamphor in chloroform with a three constant equation (Table XXI). Fig. 2 also brings out graphically the influence of chemical constitution of these compounds on the rotatory dispersion in pyridine. A more exact test of the simple dispersion formula is given by numerical calculation. The tables of rotatory dispersion (Tables I—XVIII) show that the specific rotations, observed and calculated, of the enantiomeric *oo'*-stilbenebisiminocamphors, *oo'*-stilbenebisaminocamphors, *oo'*-dibenzylbisiminocamphors, *oo'*-stilbenebisaminocamphors and *oo'*-dibenzylbisaminomethylenecamphors, in different solvents lie well within the experimental error of 0.01° in the observed angle of rotation.

The value of λ_0 , the wave-length of the hypothetical absorption band, usually in the ultraviolet region of the spectrum calculated from the dispersion formulae, may be correlated with the rotatory power of the compounds. An increase or decrease in the value of λ_0 is accompanied by a corresponding increase or decrease in the specific rotation, as is seen in the following analysis: When the conjugation is broken by the reduction of the azethenoid groups as in the conversion of *oo'*-stilbenebisiminocamphors to *oo'*-stilbenebisaminocamphors the value of λ_0 , in pyridine solution changes from 3787 to 3444 (A.U.) and the value of $[\alpha]_{\text{Hg}} (\text{green})$ decreases from 574° to 150° (Tables V and VII). In chloroform solution the very considerable shift in the wave-length of the absorption band from 3689 to 1166 (A.U.) is accompanied by the phenomenal depression in the specific rotatory power from 456.3° to 45.6° for Hg_{gr} . (Tables IV and VIII). The values of specific rotatory power and of λ_0 are higher for *oo'*-dibenzylbisiminocamphor than for *oo'*-stilbenebisiminocamphor (Tables IX—XIV; I—VI). The same relationship between the values of λ_0 and specific rotatory power is further exhibited by the remaining pair of compounds namely, *oo'*-stilbenebisaminomethylenecamphors and *oo'*-dibenzylbisaminomethylenecamphors (Tables XV, XVI; XVII, XVIII).

The Physical Identity of Enantiomers.—According to Pasteur's principle of molecular dissymmetry, enantiomorphous molecular configurations must possess the same total energy. They must show similar mechanical stability and therefore have an equal chance of being produced. They must also possess the same scalar properties; such as density, solubility, refraction, dispersion. But they must differ in those physical properties which are of directional (vectorial) nature, such as, for example, direction of rotation of the plane of polarisation of polarized light, unsymmetrical distribution of the hemihedral facets in their crystal forms, and also in the enantiomorphous distribution of pyro- and piezo-electrical polarity. On the other hand according to wave-mechanics (Temple, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1930, 26, 278) the *dextro* and *laevo* forms of a compound differ in energy and in rotatory power, although perhaps only to a very slight extent. The two views thus give different results. In support of the view derived from wave-mechanics, slight but distinct differences are alleged to exist in the rotatory power and other physical properties of *d*- and *l*-mandelic acids (Campbell and Garrow, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1930, 26, 560). But Pasteur's Law of Molecular Dissymmetry is too fundamental to be dismissed by an isolated

observation. It points to the necessity of making more observations on the equality or otherwise of the rotatory power of the *dextro*- and *laevo*-forms. The theoretical consequences emerging from such work are of fundamental importance. It is for this reason that we have made a comparative study of the rotatory power of the *dextro*- and *laevo*-isomerides of the compounds described in this and previous communications.

The individual readings of the angle of rotation did not differ from the mean by more than 0.02° . A calculation from the tables of rotatory dispersion will show that the maximum errors obtained by working out the effect on the result of the maximum deviation (0.02°) are well within the attainable limits of experimental accuracy. The maximum difference in the values of the observed specific rotatory power of the *dextro*- and *laevo*-forms of *oo'*-stilbenebisiminocamphor in acetone for Hg_{5780} (Table I), in chloroform for Na_{5893} (Table IV), and in pyridine for Li_{6104} (Table I), is 1.3° , whereas for a difference of 0.01° in the observed angle of rotation, the corresponding change in specific rotatory power is 2° . In the case of other compounds, these maximum observed differences are less than those calculated in the same way.

The inactive forms of *oo'*-stilbenebisiminocamphor, *oo'*-dibenzylbisiminocamphor and *oo'*-dibenzylbisaminomethylenecamphor melt at higher temperature than their optically active isomerides. These inactive forms are, therefore, true racemic compounds, at least in the solid state.

EXPERIMENTAL.

oo'-Stilbenebisimino-d-camphor (trans) (Formula I, Table A).

d Camphorquinone (1.66 g.) and (*trans*)-*oo'*-diaminostilbene (1.05 g.) were, in presence of fused sodium sulphate, heated at 140° — 150° for 15-20 hours. The condensed product was extracted with acetone and crystallised as yellow prismatic needles melting at 231 – 32° (yield, 1.1 g.). It is easily soluble in chloroform, pyridine and benzene; less so in acetone and difficultly soluble in methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol and ether. (Found: C, 80.51; H, 7.79; N, 5.86. $C_{34}H_{38}O_2N_2$ requires C, 80.63; H, 7.60; N, 5.53 per cent). The order of rotatory power in different solvents is as pyridine $>$ chloroform $>$ acetone $>$ ethyl alcohol $>$ methyl alcohol $>$ benzene.

oo'-Stilbenebisimino-l-camphor was prepared in the same way as the corresponding *dextro*-isomer and has the same melting point,

solubility and rotatory power (Tables I—VI). (Found: N, 5.83. $C_{34}H_{38}O_2N_2$ requires N, 5.53 per cent.).

oo'-Stilbenebisimino-*dl*-camphor was prepared in the same way as its optically active isomers and has the same crystalline form and similar solubility but melts at 238-39°. (Found: N, 5.76. $C_{34}H_{38}O_2N_2$ requires N, 5.53 per cent.).

oo'-Stilbenebisamino-*d*-camphor (Formula III, Table A).

oo'-Stilbenebisimino-*d*-camphor (1 g.) dissolved in benzene (75-80 c.c.) was shaken with zinc dust and caustic potash solution (12 %) for 20 hours, when it became colourless. The benzene layer was separated, washed with water and benzene distilled off; the residue was crystallised out of acetone as white prismatic needles (yield, 0.6 g.). It begins to decompose from 220°, melting completely at 240-41°. It is easily soluble in chloroform and pyridine; less so in acetone and benzene; and very difficultly in ethyl alcohol, methyl alcohol and ether. (Found: C, 79.86; H 8.30. $C_{34}H_{42}O_2N_2$ requires C, 80.00; H, 8.23 per cent.).

Rotatory power determinations were made only in two solvents *viz.*, pyridine and chloroform, as the compound is difficultly soluble in other solvents. Chloroform solution is slightly fluorescent, having a light blue colour in transmitted light.

oo'-Stilbenebisamino-*l*-camphor was prepared in the same way as the corresponding *dextro*-isomer and has the same melting point, solubility and rotation (Tables VII and VIII). (Found: N, 5.67. $C_{34}H_{42}O_2N_2$ requires N, 5.49 per cent.).

oo'-Stilbenebisamino-*dl*-camphor was prepared in the same way as its optically active isomers and has the same crystalline form and similar solubility but melts at 210°-12° (faintly, yellowish-white prismatic needles). (Found: N, 5.59. $C_{34}H_{42}O_2N_2$ requires N, 5.49 per cent.).

oo'-Dibenzylbisimino-*d*-camphor (Formula IV, Table A).

d-Camphorquinone (1.66 g.) and *oo'*-diaminodibenzyl hydrochloride (1.42 g.) were, in presence of fused sodium acetate, heated at 140-50° for 8 hours. The condensed product was extracted with alcohol, and crystallised as yellow prismatic needles melting at 187-88° (yield, 1.3 g.). It is readily soluble in chloroform, benzene and pyridine; less so in acetone; difficultly so in methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol and ether. (Found: C, 80.18; H, 8.10. $C_{34}H_{40}O_2N_2$ requires C, 80.32; H, 7.87 per cent.).

The order of rotatory power in different solvents is as pyridine > benzene > acetone > chloroform > ethyl alcohol > methyl alcohol.

oo'-Dibenzylbisimino-*l*-camphor was prepared in the same way as the corresponding *dextro*-isomer and has the same melting point, solubility and rotatory power in different solvents (Tables IX-XIV). (Found: N, 5.54. $C_{34}H_{40}O_2N_2$ requires N, 5.51 per cent.).

oo'-Dibenzylbisimino-*dl*-camphor was prepared in the same way as its optically active isomers and has the same crystalline form and similar solubility but melts at 194-95°. (Found: N, 5.72. $C_{34}H_{40}O_2N_2$ requires N, 5.51 per cent.).

oo'-Dibenzylbisamino-*d*-camphor (Formula VI, Table A).—*oo'*-Dibenzylbisimino-*d*-camphor (1.0 g.) dissolved in benzene was reduced in the usual way with 12% potassium hydroxide and zinc dust. Dry hydrochloric acid gas was passed through benzene solution when a black gummy solid separated. It was insoluble in water and turned brown. The suspended solid was neutralised with ammonium hydrate and the precipitate crystallised out of acetone as light cream coloured prismatic needles melting at 214-16° (yield, 0.45 g.). It is easily soluble in chloroform; less so in pyridine and benzene; difficultly soluble in acetone; sparingly soluble in methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol and ether. (Found: C, 79.49; H, 8.83. $C_{34}H_{44}O_2N_2$ requires C, 79.69; H, 8.59 per cent.).

Rotatory power determinations were made only in three solvents *viz.*, chloroform, pyridine and benzene. as the compound is difficultly soluble in other solvents.

oo'-Dibenzylbisamino-*l*-camphor was prepared in the same way as the corresponding *dextro*-isomer and has the same melting point, solubility and rotatory power in different solvents (Table XIX-XXI). (Found: N, 5.65. $C_{34}H_{44}O_2N_2$ requires N, 5.47 per cent.).

oo'-Dibenzylbisamino-*dl*-camphor was prepared in the same way as its optically active isomers and has the same crystalline form and similar solubility but melts at 204-05°. (Found: N, 5.64. $C_{34}H_{44}O_2N_2$ requires N, 5.47 per cent.).

oo'-Stilbenebisaminomethylene-*d*-camphor (Formula II, Table A).—*oo'*-Diaminostilbene (0.5 g.) in glacial acetic acid was added to a concentrated solution of oxymethylene-*d*-camphor (0.9 g.) in alcohol when a yellow precipitate separated at once. It was crystallised out of pyridine as shining light yellow prisms melting at 295-96° (yield,

0.9 g.). It is fairly soluble in chloroform; less so in pyridine; and sparingly soluble in methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol, acetone, benzene, ether, and glacial acetic acid. (Found: C, 80.90; H, 8.22. $C_{36}H_{42}O_2N_2$ requires C, 80.91; H, 7.86 per cent.).

Rotatory power determinations were made only in two solvents *viz.*, chloroform and pyridine, the substance being very insoluble in other solvents.

oo'-Stilbenebisaminomethylene-*l*-camphor was prepared in the same way as the corresponding *dextro*-isomer and has the same melting point, solubility and rotation (Tables XV and XVI). (Found: N, 5.26. $C_{36}H_{42}O_2N_2$ requires N, 5.24 per cent.).

oo'-Stilbenebisaminomethylene-*dl*-camphor was prepared in the same way as its optically active isomers and has the same melting point and similar solubility. (Found: N, 5.47. $C_{36}H_{42}O_2N_2$ requires N, 5.24 per cent.).

oo'-Dibenzylbisaminomethylene-*d*-camphor (Formula V, Table A). —*oo'*-Diaminodibenzyl (0.55 g.) in 50% acetic acid was added to a concentrated solution of oxymethylene-*d*-camphor (0.95 g.) in alcohol when an almost white precipitate separated at once. It was crystallised out of benzene as shining faintly yellowish-white prisms melting at 266-68° (yield 0.8 g.). It is fairly soluble in chloroform; less soluble in pyridine and sparingly soluble in benzene, methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol, acetone and ether. (Found: C, 80.50; H, 8.40; N, 5.28. $C_{36}H_{44}O_2N_2$ requires C, 80.60; H, 8.21; N, 5.23 per cent.).

Rotatory power determinations were made only in two solvents *viz.*, chloroform and pyridine, the compound being insoluble in other solvents.

oo'-Dibenzylbisaminomethylene-*l*-camphor was prepared in the same way as the corresponding *dextro*-isomer and has the same melting point, solubility and rotatory power (Tables XVII and XVIII). (Found: N, 5.30. $C_{36}H_{44}O_2N_2$ requires N, 5.23 per cent.).

oo'-Dibenzylbisaminomethylene-*dl*-camphor was prepared in the same way as its optically active isomers and has the same crystalline form and similar solubility but melts at 272-73°. (Found: N, 5.30. $C_{36}H_{44}O_2N_2$ requires N, 5.23 per cent.).

The rotatory power determinations were made in a 2 dcm. jacketed tube at 35°. The value of λ_0 , calculated from the dispersion formula, is given in the tables and is expressed as μ or 10^{-4} cm.

TABLE I.

oo'-Stilbenebisiminocamphor in Acetone.

$$[\alpha] = \frac{63.68}{\lambda^2 - 0.1502} ; \lambda_0 = 0.3876.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	Calc. [α] =c.	<i>Laevo</i>		
Concentration : g/100 c.c.	Obs. [α] =o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. [α] =o'.	Concentration : g/100 c.c.
0.2496	430.6°	+0.4°	Hg ₅₄₆₁	± 430.2°	± 0°	-430.6°	0.2520
"	346.5	+0.4	Hg ₅₇₈₀	346.1	-0.9	345.2	"
"	322.5	-0.4	Na ₅₈₉₃	322.9	+0.5	323.4	"
"	286.4	+0.1	Li ₆₁₀₄	286.3	-0.5	285.8	"
"	240.4	-0.4	Cd ₆₄₃₈	240.8	-0.7	240.1	"
"	212.3	± 0	Li ₆₇₀₈	212.3	± 0	212.3	"

TABLE II.

oo'-Stilbenebisiminocamphor in Methyl Alcohol.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{58.61}{\lambda^2 - 0.1458} ; \lambda_0 = 0.3818.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	Calc. [α] =c.	<i>Laevo</i>		
Concentration : g/100 c.c.	Obs. [α] =o.	o-c.			o-c.	Obs. [α] =o'.	Concentration : g/100 c.c.
0.1272	385.2°	+0.4°	Hg ₅₄₆₁	± 384.8°	-1.4°	-383.4°	0.1252
"	310.7	-0.6	Hg ₅₇₈₀	311.3	+0.3	311.6	"
"	290.9	± 0	Na ₅₈₉₃	290.9	+0.7	291.6	"
"	259.4	+1.0	Li ₆₁₀₄	258.4	+1.2	259.6	"
"	220.2	+2.4	Cd ₆₄₃₈	217.8	+1.9	219.7	"
"	192.7	± 0	Li ₆₇₀₈	192.7	-1.0	191.7	"

The compound was sparingly soluble in methyl alcohol ; hence half the usual concentration was employed.

TABLE III.

oo'-Stilbenebisiminocamphor in Benzene.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{42.06}{\lambda^2 - 0.1456} ; \lambda_0 = 0.3816.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	Calc. [α] =c.	<i>Laevo</i>		
Concentration : g/100 c.c.	Obs. [α] =o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. [α] =o'.	Concentration : g/100 c.c.
0.2520	275.8°	+0.3°	Hg ₅₄₆₁	± 275.5°	+0.5°	-276.0°	0.2500
"	222.2	-0.9	Hg ₅₇₈₀	223.1	-1.1	222.0	"
"	208.4	± 0	Na ₅₈₉₃	208.4	-0.4	208.0	"
"	184.5	-0.7	Li ₆₁₀₄	185.2	+0.8	186.0	"
"	156.8	+0.4	Cd ₆₄₃₈	156.4	-0.4	156.0	"
"	138.9	+0.8	Li ₆₇₀₈	138.1	-0.1	138.0	"

TABLE IV.

oo'-Stilbenebisiminocamphor in Chloroform.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{74.04}{\lambda^2 - 0.1361} ; \lambda_0 = 0.3689.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	Calc. $[\alpha]$ = c.	<i>Laevo</i>		
Concentration : g/100 c.c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ = o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ = o'.	Concentration : g/100 c.c.
0.2520	456.3°	-0.4°	Hg ₅₄₆₁	±456.7°	-0.7°	-456.0°	0.2500
"	373.1	-0.9	Hg ₅₇₈₀	374.0	±0	374.0	"
"	351.3	+0.8	Na ₅₈₉₃	350.5	-0.5	350.0	"
"	313.5	+0.4	Li ₆₁₀₄	313.1	+0.9	314.0	"
"	265.9	-0.2	Cd ₆₄₃₈	266.1	-0.1	266.0	"
"	236.1	+0.3	Li ₆₇₀₈	235.8	+0.2	236.0	"

TABLE V.

oo'-Stilbenebisiminocamphor in Pyridine.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{88.90}{\lambda^2 - 0.1434} ; \lambda_0 = 0.3787.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	Calc. $[\alpha]$ = c.	<i>Laevo</i>		
Concentration : g/100 c.c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ = o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ = o'.	Concentration : g/100 c.c.
0.2512	574.1°	±0°	Hg ₅₄₆₁	±574.1°	-0.7°	-573.4°	0.2520
"	465.8	-0.3	Hg ₅₇₈₀	466.1	+0.2	466.3	"
"	436.0	±0	Na ₅₈₉₃	436.0	+0.5	436.5	"
"	388.2	+0.4	Li ₆₁₀₄	387.8	-0.9	386.9	"
"	328.5	+0.7	Cd ₆₄₃₈	327.8	-0.4	327.4	"
"	290.7	+0.8	Li ₆₇₀₈	289.9	-0.2	289.7	"

TABLE VI.

oo'-Stilbenebisiminocamphor in Ethyl Alcohol.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{62.37}{\lambda^2 - 0.1369} ; \lambda_0 = 0.3700.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	Calc. $[\alpha]$ = c.	<i>Laevo</i>		
Concentration : g/100 c.c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ = o.	o-c.			o-c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ = o.	Concentration : g/100 c.c.
0.2500	392.0°	-0.9°	Hg ₅₄₆₁	±392.9°	±0	-392.9°	0.2520
"	322.0	+0.6	Hg ₅₇₈₀	321.4	±0	321.4	"
"	302.0	+0.8	Na ₅₈₉₃	301.2	+0.2	301.4	"
"	268.0	-0.8	Li ₆₁₀₄	268.8	-0.9	267.9	"
"	228.0	-0.3	Cd ₆₄₃₈	228.3	-0.1	228.2	"
"	202.0	-0.4	Li ₆₇₀₈	202.4	±0	202.4	"

TABLE VII.

oo'-Stilbenebisaminocamphor in Pyridine.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{26.93}{\lambda^2 - 0.1186} ; \lambda_0 = 0.3444.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	Calc. $[\alpha]$ =c.	<i>Laevo</i>		
Concentration: g/100 c.c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o'.	Concentration: g/100 c.c.
0.5008	239.6°	-1.2°	Cd ₄₈₀₀	±240.8°	-0.7	-240.1°	0.5050
"	192.7	+0.4	Cd ₅₀₈₆	192.3	+0.4	192.7	"
"	175.7	-0.7	Ag ₅₂₀₉	176.4	-0.5	175.9	"
"	149.8	-0.2	Hg ₅₄₆₁	150.0	+0.2	150.2	"
"	124.8	-0.1	Hg ₅₇₈₀	124.9	-0.4	124.5	"
"	118.8	+1.1	Na ₅₈₉₃	117.7	-0.1	117.6	"
"	105.8	-0.1	Li ₆₁₀₄	106.0	-0.2	105.8	"
"	91.87	+0.86	Cd ₆₄₃₈	91.01	-0.11	90.9	"
"	81.81	+0.54	Li ₆₇₀₈	81.27	-0.26	81.01	"

TABLE VIII.

oo'-Stilbenebisaminocamphor in Chloroform.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{12.94}{\lambda^2 - 0.0136} ; \lambda_0 = 0.1166.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	Calc. $[\alpha]$ =c.	<i>Laevo</i>		
Concentration: g/100 c.c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o'.	Concentration: g/100 c.c.
0.5040	60.52°	+0.82°	Cd ₄₈₈₀	±59.70°	+1.4°	-61.0°	0.5000
"	52.59	-0.22	Cd ₅₀₈₆	52.81	+0.19	53.0	"
"	49.61	-0.62	Ag ₅₂₀₉	50.23	-0.23	50.0	"
"	45.64	+0.16	Hg ₅₄₆₁	45.48	+0.52	46.0	"
"	40.68	+0.29	Hg ₅₇₈₀	40.39	+0.61	41.0	"
"	38.70	-0.10	Na ₅₈₉₃	38.80	+0.20	39.0	"
"	35.72	-0.34	Li ₆₁₀₄	36.06	-0.06	36.0	"
"	32.75	+0.47	Dd ₆₄₃₈	32.28	+0.72	33.0	"
"	29.76	+0.10	Li ₆₇₀₈	29.66	+0.34	30.0	"

TABLE IX.

oo'-Dibenzylbisiminocamphor in Benzene.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{105.3}{\lambda^2 - 0.1684} ; \lambda_0 = 0.4104.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	Calc. $[\alpha]$ =c.	<i>Laevo</i>		
Concentration: g/100 c.c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o'.	Concentration: g/100 c.c.
0.4024	811.4°	-0.2°	Hg ₅₄₆₁	±811.6°	-0.4°	-811.2°	0.4032
"	634.9	-0.8	Hg ₅₇₈₀	635.7	-0.6	635.1	"
"	590.2	+1.4	Na ₅₈₉₃	588.8	+1.5	590.3	"
"	516.9	+1.0	Li ₆₁₀₄	515.9	+1.2	517.1	"
"	427.4	-0.7	Cd ₆₄₃₈	428.1	-0.2	427.9	"
"	374.1	-0.3	Li ₆₇₀₈	374.4	+0.1	374.5	"

TABLE X.

oo'-Dibenzylbisiminocamphor in Chloroform.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{92.72}{\lambda^2 - 0.1625} ; \lambda_0 = 0.4031.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	Calc. $[\alpha]$ =c.	<i>Laevo</i>		
Concentration : g/100 c.c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o'.	Concentration : g/100 c.c.
0.4012°	684.1°	+0.7°	Hg ₅₄₆₁	±683.4°	+0.4°	-683.8°	0.4000
"	539.6	-0.9	Hg ₅₇₈₀	540.5	+0.8	541.3	"
"	502.3	+0.5	Na ₅₈₉₃	501.8	-0.5	501.3	"
"	441.2	-0.2	Li ₆₁₀₄	441.4	+1.1	442.5	"
"	368.9	+0.9	Cd ₆₄₃₈	368.0	-0.5	367.5	"
"	321.6	-0.9	Li ₆₇₀₈	322.5	± 0	322.5	"

TABLE XI.

oo'-Dibenzylbisiminocamphor in Pyridine.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{112.8}{\lambda^2 - 0.1704} ; \lambda_0 = 0.4128.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	Calc. $[\alpha]$ =o'	<i>Laevo</i>		
Concentration : g/100 c.c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o'.	Concentration : g/100 c.c.
0.4020	880.4°	-1.4°	Hg ₅₄₆₁	±881.8°	+0.2°	-882.0°	0.4048
"	690.2	+1.3	Hg ₅₇₈₀	688.9	+0.4	689.3	"
"	638.0	+0.5	Na ₅₈₉₃	637.5	-0.1	637.4	"
"	557.2	-0.5	Li ₆₁₀₄	557.7	-0.5	557.2	"
"	462.7	+0.8	Cd ₆₄₃₈	461.9	+0.1	462.0	"
"	401.8	-1.5	Li ₆₇₀₈	403.3	-0.6	402.7	"

TABLE XII.

oo'-Dibenzylbisiminocamphor in Ethyl Alcohol.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{83.99}{\lambda^2 - 0.1642} ; \lambda_0 = 0.4052.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	Calc. $[\alpha]$ =c.	<i>Laevo</i>		
Concentration : g/100 c.c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o'.	Concentration : g/100 c.c.
0.2020	626.2°	-0.7°	Hg ₅₄₆₁	±626.9°	+0.6°	-627.5°	0.2000
"	495.0	+0.7	Hg ₅₇₈₀	494.3	+0.7	495.0	"
"	458.0	-0.6	Na ₅₈₉₃	458.6	-1.1	457.5	"
"	403.4	+0.4	Li ₆₁₀₄	403.0	-0.5	402.5	"
"	335.4	-0.2	Cd ₆₄₃₈	335.6	-0.6	335.0	"
"	294.5	+0.5	Li ₆₇₀₈	294.0	+1.0	295.0	"

TABLE XIII.

oo'-Dibenzylbisiminocamphor in Acetone.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{99.88}{\lambda^2 - 0.1628} ; \lambda_0 = 0.4035.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	Calc. [α] = c .	<i>Laevo</i>		
Concentration : g/100 c.c.	Obs. [α] = o .	$o-c$.			$o'-c$.	Obs. [α] = o' .	Concentration : g/100 c.c.
0.4056	738.4°	+0.9°	Hg ₅₄₆₁	$\pm 737.5^\circ$	$\pm 0.0^\circ$	-737.5°	0.4020
"	581.9	-1.1	Hg ₅₇₈₀	583.0	-2.2	580.8	"
"	541.2	-0.2	Na ₅₈₉₃	541.4	-0.3	541.1	"
"	475.8	+0.3	Li ₆₁₀₄	476.1	-1.0	475.1	"
"	397.0	-0.2	Cd ₆₄₃₈	396.8	-1.3	395.5	"
"	347.7	± 0	Li ₆₇₀₈	347.7	-0.8	346.9	"

TABLE XIV.

oo'-Dibenzylbisiminocamphor in Methyl Alcohol.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{80.26}{\lambda^2 - 0.1680} ; \lambda_0 = 0.4099.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	Calc. [α] = c .	<i>Laevo</i>		
Concentration : g/100 c.c.	Obs. [α] = o .	$o-c$.			$o'-o$.	Obs. [α] = o' .	Concentration : g/100 c.c.
0.2016	615.2°	-1.0°	Hg ₅₄₆₁	$\pm 616.2^\circ$	-1.0°	-615.2°	0.2040
"	483.7	+0.5	Hg ₅₇₈₀	483.2	-0.4	482.8	"
"	447.9	+0.3	Na ₅₈₉₃	447.6	+0.9	448.5	"
"	391.9	-0.3	Li ₆₁₀₄	392.2	-0.1	392.1	"
"	324.9	-0.7	Cd ₆₄₃₈	325.6	+0.4	326.0	"
"	285.2	+0.6	Li ₆₇₀₈	284.6	-0.3	284.3	"

TABLE XV.

oo'-Stilbenebisaminomethylenecamphor in Chloroform.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{57.12}{\lambda^2 - 0.1532} ; \lambda_0 = 0.3914.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	Calc. [α] = c .	<i>Laevo</i>		
Concentration : g/100 c.c.	Obs. [α] = o .	$o-c$.			$o'-c$.	Obs. [α] = o' .	Concentration : g/100 c.c.
0.4048	541.2°	-0.4°	Cd ₅₀₈₆	$\pm 541.6^\circ$	+0.9°	-542.5°	0.4000
"	483.1	-0.6	Ag ₅₂₀₉	483.7	+0.1	483.8	"
"	394.0	± 0	Hg ₅₄₆₁	394.0	-0.2	393.8	"
"	316.2	+0.4	Hg ₅₇₈₀	315.8	-0.8	315.0	"
"	294.1	-0.1	Na ₅₈₉₃	294.2	+0.8	295.0	"
"	260.7	+0.3	Li ₆₁₀₄	260.4	-0.4	260.0	"
"	218.7	+0.4	Cd ₆₄₃₈	218.6	+0.2	218.8	"
"	191.4	-1.0	Li ₆₇₀₈	192.4	+0.1	192.5	"

The solution did not exhibit mutarotation.

TABLE XVI.

oo'-Stilbenebisaminomethylenecamphor in Pyridine.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{63.02}{\lambda^2 - 0.153} ; \lambda_0 = 0.3911.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	Calc. $[\alpha]$ =c.	<i>Leavo</i>		
Concentration : g/100 c.c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o'.	Concentration : g/100 c.c.
0.2056	530.3°	-2.4°	Ag ₅₂₀₉	±532.7°	+0.5°	-533.2°	0.2016
	435.4	+1.4	Hg ₅₄₆₁	434.0	-0.2	433.8	
	347.7	-0.3	Hg ₅₇₈₀	348.0	-0.8	347.2	
	325.9	+1.4	Na ₅₈₉₃	324.5	+0.4	324.9	
	287.0	±0	Li ₆₁₀₄	287.0	+0.7	287.7	
	240.7	-0.4	Cd ₆₄₃₈	241.1	-0.5	240.6	
	211.5	-0.6	Li ₆₇₀₈	212.1	+1.2	213.3	

The solution exhibited mutarotation ; $[\alpha]_{\text{Hg}_{5461}} = 435.4^\circ$ and $[\alpha]_{\text{Hg}_{5780}} = 347.7^\circ$ changing to 413.3° and 328.2° respectively in course of 15 hours. The change is accompanied with the deepening of the initial pale yellow colour.

Half the usual concentration was employed, the substance being difficultly soluble in pyridine.

TABLE XVII.

oo'-Dibenzylbisaminomethylenecamphor in Chloroform.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{59.78}{\lambda^2 - 0.1455} ; \lambda_0 = 0.3814.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	Calc. $[\alpha]$ =c.	<i>Leavo</i>		
Concentration : g/100 c.c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o.	o-c.			o'-c.	Obs. $[\alpha]$ =o'.	Concentration : g/100 c.c.
0.4040	527.2°	-0.9°	Cd ₆₀₈₆	±528.1°	+0.7°	-528.8°	0.4000
"	475.2	-0.1	Ag ₅₂₀₉	475.3	+1.0	476.3	"
"	392.3	+0.8	Hg ₅₄₆₁	391.5	-0.2	391.3	"
"	316.8	-0.2	Hg ₅₇₈₀	317.0	-0.7	316.3	"
"	295.8	-0.5	Na ₅₈₉₃	296.3	±0	296.3	"
"	263.6	+0.4	Li ₆₁₀₄	263.2	-0.7	262.5	"
"	222.8	+0.6	Cd ₆₄₃₈	222.2	-0.9	221.3	"
"	195.5	-0.4	Li ₆₇₀₈	195.9	+0.4	196.3	"

The solution does not exhibit any mutarotation.

TABLE XVIII.

oo'-Dibenzylbisaminomethylenecamphor in Pyridine.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{56.59}{\lambda^2 - 0.1472}; \quad \lambda_0 = 0.3837.$$

<i>Dextro</i>				<i>Levo</i>			
Concentration : g/100 c.c.	Obs. [α] = o	o-c.	Line.	Calc. [α] = c.	o'-c.	Obs. [α] = o'.	Concentration : g/100 c.c.
0.2044	506.3°	-1.4°	Cd ₅₀₈₆	± 507.7°	+1.2°	-508.9°	0.2024
"	457.3	+1.2	Ag ₅₂₀₉	456.1	-1.7	454.4	"
"	374.2	-0.6	Hg ₅₄₆₁	374.8	+0.6	375.4	"
"	303.3	+0.5	Hg ₅₇₈₀	302.8	+1.0	303.8	"
"	283.7	+0.8	Na ₅₈₉₃	282.9	-1.3	281.6	"
"	251.9	+0.8	Li ₆₁₀₄	251.1	-1.6	249.5	"
"	210.3	-1.3	Cd ₆₄₃₈	211.7	+0.7	212.4	"
"	185.9	-1.0	Li ₆₇₀₈	186.9	-1.7	185.2	"

TABLE XIX.

oo'-Dibenzylbisaminocamphor in Pyridine.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{3.28}{\lambda^2 - 0.5390} \pm \frac{40.73}{\lambda^2}; \quad \lambda_0 = 0.7342.$$

<i>Dextro</i>				<i>Levo</i>			
Concentration : g/100 c.c.	Obs. [α] = o	o-c.	Line.	Calc. [α] = c.	o'-c.	Obs. [α] = o'.	Concentration : g/100 c.c.
0.2040	147.1°	+1.3°	Cd ₅₀₈₆	± 145.8°	+1.7°	-147.5°	0.2000
"	134.8	-3.0	Ag ₅₂₀₉	137.8	-2.8	135.0	"
"	122.6	-0.3	Hg ₅₄₆₁	122.9	-0.4	122.5	"
"	107.8	+1.9	Hg ₅₇₈₀	105.9	+1.6	107.5	"
"	100.5	+0.3	Na ₅₈₉₃	100.2	-0.2	100.0	"
"	85.83	-3.8	Li ₆₁₀₄	89.6	-4.6	85.0	"
"	68.63	-3.2	Cd ₆₄₃₈	71.8	-1.8	70.00	"
"	53.92	+0.2	Li ₆₇₀₈	53.7	+1.3	55.00	"

Half the usual concentration was employed.

TABLE XX.

oo'-Dibenzylbisaminocamphor in Benzene.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{35.97}{\lambda^2 - 1.424} \pm \frac{57.12}{\lambda^2}; \quad \lambda_0 = 1.1935.$$

<i>Dextro</i>				<i>Levo</i>			
Concentration : g/100 c.c.	Obs. [α] = o.	o-c.	Line	Calc. [α] = c.	o'-c.	Obs. [α] = o'.	Concentration : g/100 c.c.
0.1992	190.7°	± 0°	Cd ₅₀₈₆	± 190.7°	+0.5°	-191.2°	0.2040
"	178.2	-1.7	Ag ₅₂₀₉	179.9	-1.1	178.8	"
"	161.8	+1.5	Hg ₅₄₆₁	160.3	+2.7	163.0	"
"	138.0	-0.6	Hg ₅₇₈₀	138.6	-1.3	137.3	"
"	130.5	-1.2	Na ₅₈₉₃	131.7	-1.8	129.9	"
"	120.5	+0.8	Li ₆₁₀₄	119.7	+0.6	120.3	"
"	105.4	+2.7	Cd ₆₄₃₈	102.7	+2.7	105.4	"
"	90.36	-0.14	Li ₆₇₀₈	90.50	+0.17	90.67	"

TABLE XXI.

oo'-Dibenzylbisaminocamphor in Chloroform.

Concentration : g/100 c.c.	Line.	Obs. [α] <i>Dextro</i> (d).	Obs. [α] <i>Leavo</i> (l).	Difference <i>d-l</i> .
0.3980 (<i>dextro</i>)	Cd ₄₈₈₀	+226.4°	-225.0°	+1.4°
0.4000 (<i>leavo</i>)	Cd ₅₀₈₆	187.2	187.5	-0.3
	Ag ₅₂₀₉	172.1	172.5	-0.4
	Hg ₅₄₆₁	157.0	157.5	-0.5
	Hg ₅₇₈₀	133.1	133.8	-0.7
	Na ₅₈₉₃	121.9	121.3	+0.6
	Li ₆₁₀₄	109.2	108.8	+0.4
	Cd ₆₄₃₈	99.24	98.8	+0.44
	Li ₆₇₀₈	81.66	81.3	+0.36

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